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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

SYMPOSIUM

FRONTIERS IN REACTION ENGINEERING

Novel Insights for Sustainable Production

Tuesday, 25 November 2025
Lancaster University, UK

ABOUT THE SYMPOSIUM

IChemE's Catalysis & Reaction Engineering Special Interest Group (CatSIG) and the School of Engineering at Lancaster University host a one-day symposium on sustainable catalysis, CO₂ conversion, hydrogen, electrified and intensified reactors — driving innovation, collaboration, and future energy solutions.

The event welcomes PhD students, early-career academics, and industrialists to present their research on the latest developments in cutting-edge catalysis and reaction engineering.

This symposium focuses on emerging trends shaping the future of sustainable chemical technologies and energy conversion.

Topics of interest include:

- Electrification of catalysis and electrochemical reactors
- External field-assisted (plasma, photo, magnetic, etc.) catalytic processes
- Catalysis for carbon dioxide conversion
- Catalytic hydrogen production and storage
- Intensified reactor technologies for advanced decarbonisation

Through presentations and networking sessions, this event offers a platform to showcase innovation, foster collaboration, and explore future directions in reaction engineering.

OVERVIEW OF THE SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

Founded in 1969, the School has evolved into a dynamic centre for engineering research and education, with **sustainable engineering, chemical engineering, nuclear engineering and bioengineering** at the core of our vision. We are entering an exciting period of growth as we enhance our commitment to research excellence, inclusivity and innovative teaching.

Our heritage in general engineering underpins a strong interdisciplinary ethos. Our academic community brings together expertise across engineering, science and technology, including chemical engineering, bioengineering, sustainable engineering, applied mathematics, chemistry, physics, materials science, design, mechanical engineering, mechatronics, and electronics. This breadth enables us to tackle complex challenges through integrated, cross-disciplinary approaches.

Through strong local and international partnerships, we integrate research, knowledge exchange and teaching to broaden our impact. We pride ourselves on being one of the most diverse and supportive engineering communities in the UK.

LOCAL ORGANISATION COMMITTEE

- Dr Farid Aiouache
- Dr Luigi Carlo Capozzi
- Dr Giuseppe Bagnato

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IChemE ORGANISATION COMMITTEE

- Dr James McGregor, chair of the IChemE Catalysis & Reaction Engineering Special Interest Group

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

- Aaron Martin, IChemE SIG Member Engagement Officer
- Debbie Brannan, IChemE Member Support Advisor
- Dr Megan Jobson, former IChemE Learned Society Manager

PROGRAMME OF THE EVENT

■ 09:30 – 10:10 Registration, Coffee, and Networking

Chair: Dr. Giuseppe Bagnato

■ 10:10 – 10:30 Welcome and Introduction

Dr Farid Aiouache (Lancaster University), Chris Lambert (Director of Engagement and co-ordinator of the Industry Advisory Board, Lancaster University), Dr Luigi Capozzi, Dr Giuseppe Bagnato, and Dr James McGregor (University of Sheffield, Chair of CatSIG)

■ 10:30 – 11:20 *Dr Jack Williams (Head Engineer, Syntholene Energy Ltd.) “Electro-Sustainable Aviation Fuel (eSAF) Engineering: Magnetic Resonance Insights and Breakthroughs Toward Cost-Competitive eSAF”*

■ 11:20 – 12:10 *Dr Sourav Chatterjee (Lecturer, University of Bath, Department of Chemical Engineering) “Application of AI-Guided Automated Flow Chemical Platforms for Understanding Complex Chemical Systems”*

■ 12:10 – 12:20 Break

■ 12:20 – 13:00 *Dr Farid Aiouache (Lancaster University) “Synergistic Energy–Process Integration for Catalytic Reactor Intensification”*

■ 13:00 – 13:45 Lunch and Networking

Chair: Dr. Luigi Capozzi

■ 13:45 – 14:35 *Dr Dongda Zhang (University of Manchester) “Reaction Engineering in the Era of AI and Digitalisation – From Predictive Modelling to Discovery and Generative Design”*

■ 14:35 – 15:15 *Dr Giuseppe Bagnato (Lancaster University) “Chemical Reaction Engineering for Net Zero Carbon”*

■ 15:15 – 15:30 Break

■ 15:30 – 16:00 Researcher Presentations

- *Zahra Ilkhani: “Bio-redox based leaching of precious metals from e-wastes”*
- *Steve McGowan: “Modelling uranium reactive separation from seawater”*

■ 16:00 – 16:30 Networking, Refreshments, and Closing Remarks

Electro-Sustainable Aviation Fuel (eSAF) Engineering: Magnetic Resonance Insights and Breakthroughs Toward Cost-Competitive eSAF

Dr Jack Williams

Head Engineer, Syntholene Energy Ltd., UK

Biography

Dr Jack Williams began his studies in 2012 at Imperial College London, completing an MEng in Chemical Engineering that included a year abroad at the University of Queensland, Australia. In 2016, he joined the Department of Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology at the University of Cambridge to pursue a PhD under the supervision of Professor Dame Lynn Gladden in the Magnetic Resonance Research Group, supported by research funding from Shell and in close collaboration with the Shell Energy Transition Campus Amsterdam (ETCA). He subsequently undertook a four year Postdoctoral Research Associateship funded jointly by Shell and the IChemE Andrew Fellowship, awarded for promising research in heterogeneous catalysis. In January 2025, Jack became a founding member and Head Engineer at Syntholene Energy, a US based startup developing next generation eFuels by integrating high efficiency reactor systems with low cost geothermal energy resources.

Abstract

This work shows how recent advances in electrolysis, catalytic science, and reaction engineering are converging to enable cost-competitive electro-Sustainable Aviation Fuel (eSAF). Magnetic resonance (MR) imaging and diffusion studies of operating PEM electrolyzers and Fischer–Tropsch reactors are presented, and it is shown that spatially resolved transport heterogeneities, catalyst level product distributions, and chain growth behaviour can be directly observed in operando, yielding new mechanistic insight and improving industrial reaction modelling. Advances in high temperature solid oxide electrolysis, multifunctional CO₂-to-fuel catalysts, methanol-to-jet pathways, and modular reactor technologies are then highlighted as key enablers of scalable eFuel synthesis. Finally, it is shown that coupling these high efficiency unit operations to abundant geothermal heat and power, as pursued in Syntholene Energy's geothermal-to-liquid eFuel concept, offers a viable pathway toward low cost, carbon neutral jet fuel production.

Application of AI-Guided Automated Flow Chemical Platforms for Understanding Complex Chemical Systems

Dr Sourav Chatterjee

University of Bath, Department of Chemical Engineering

Biography

Dr. Chatterjee is a Lecturer of Chemical Engineering at the University of Bath and the Principal Investigator of the AI/ML-guided Automated Flow Synthesis Lab. He is also the Director and Co-Founder of SOM-C LTD, a technology company based in Bath developing AI-driven automated flow platforms for advanced chemical discovery.

Prior to his current roles, Dr. Chatterjee served as Team Leader of Automation and AI in Chemistry and Catalysis at ETH Zurich, where he developed machine learning workflows for the Swiss Catalysis Hub East and secured NCCR Catalysis funding to establish an open research data management platform. He has led and managed research projects funded by the ERC and DARPA, published in leading journals such as JACS and Nature, and received a postdoctoral research fellowship from the Max Planck Society in Germany.

Abstract

Automated synthesis platforms accelerate and simplify the preparation of molecules by removing the physical barriers to organic synthesis. This provides unrestricted access to biopolymers and small molecules via reproducible and directly comparable chemical processes. Current automated multistep syntheses rely on either iterative or linear processes, and require compromises in terms of versatility and the use of equipment. I will present an approach towards the automated single and multistep synthesis based on a series of continuous flow modules that are radially arranged around a central switching station. Sequential, non-simultaneous reactions can be combined to perform multistep processes, enabling the use of variable flow rates, reuse of reactors under different conditions, and the storage of intermediates. The capabilities of this approach are demonstrated by performing optimizations and multistep syntheses of targets, varying concentrations via inline dilutions, exploring several strategies- different reaction pathways and chemistries, and using the same reagents to perform synthesis without instrument reconfiguration. Data from these automated synthesizers are used to train machine learning models for prediction of stereoselectivity.

Synergistic Energy–Process Integration for Catalytic Reactor Intensification

Dr Farid Aiouache

Lancaster University, School of Engineering

Biography

Dr Farid Aiouache is a Senior Lecturer and holds M.Eng, MSc, and PhD degrees from Nagoya University, Japan. He integrates science and engineering in reactor design to develop intensified processes that reduce plant size, energy use, waste, and environmental impact while enhancing safety and sustainability. His research spans transport phenomena and operando reactor sensing, in situ activation using light, magnetic, and electric fields, compact plant design integrating reaction and separation—including hydrogen isotopic exchange for water detritiation—dynamic operations via optical laser tomography, and functional material design for sustainable energy. Farid has over eighty peer-reviewed publications and leads projects in CO₂ capture, green solvents, energy conversion, and recovery of valuable metals from waste, supported by industrial and council grants.

Abstract

This presentation demonstrates how multi-scale reaction engineering enables sustainable chemical processes with reduced environmental impact. By integrating catalyst design and chemical engineering across temporal, structural, and functional domains, process efficiency can be drastically increased. Advanced experimental techniques, including spatially resolved mass spectrometry, near-infrared imaging, and optical diffuse tomography, coupled with 3D computational fluid dynamics modelling, reveal local phenomena that traditional 1D models cannot capture. Case studies include CO₂ adsorption in zeolite 13X packed beds, catalytic distillation with *in-situ* water removal, alumina sol-gel coating for reactive static mixers, and photocatalytic rotating disc reactors. Results demonstrate that reactor intensification through multifunctional reactors and process-catalyst interactions significantly improves atom, mass, and energy efficiency. Science-based multi-scale approaches are essential for addressing global environmental challenges and enabling rational scale-up of novel reactor technologies.

Reaction Engineering in the Era of AI and Digitalisation – From Predictive Modelling to Discovery and Generative Design

Dr Dongda Zhang

University of Manchester, School of Chemical Engineering and Analytical Science

Biography

Dr Dongda Zhang is a Lecturer in Chemical Engineering and Machine Learning at the University of Manchester and a Royal Academy of Engineering Industrial Fellow. His research bridges chemical engineering, artificial intelligence, and digital manufacturing, with a focus on interpretable AI, scientific machine learning, data-driven optimisation, and system-level knowledge discovery. He is particularly interested in integrating advanced data intelligence techniques with domain expertise to accelerate inverse design, prediction, optimisation, and scale-up of novel chemical and biochemical reaction systems.

Abstract

In this talk, I will discuss how machine learning and data intelligence can address key industrial challenges in reaction engineering. I will focus on how predictive, discovery, and generative AI methods can tackle critical issues in chemical and biochemical reaction systems. The presentation will cover hybrid modelling for dynamic prediction and optimisation of industrial reaction processes, interpretable AI and augmented intelligence for the automatic discovery of global rate models for new reaction systems, and the application of generative AI techniques to design novel molecules and identify promising synthetic pathways. Examples spanning both near-term and long-term challenges will be presented, and future opportunities for integrating AI into reaction engineering research will be highlighted.

Chemical Reaction Engineering for Net Zero Carbon

Dr Giuseppe Bagnato

Lancaster University, School of Engineering

Biography

Dr Giuseppe Bagnato is a Lecturer in Chemical Engineering at Lancaster University, with research expertise spanning catalytic process engineering, biomass valorisation, hydrogen production and storage, CO₂ utilisation, and membrane reactor technologies. His work focuses on developing sustainable and low-carbon chemical processes, with a particular emphasis on catalytic upgrading of biomass-derived feedstocks, hydrogenation mechanisms, techno-economic assessments, and process intensification strategies.

Giuseppe has over 15 years of international research experience across the UK, Italy, the Netherlands, and Sweden. He has published extensively in high-impact journals, authored multiple book chapters, and guest-edited several special issues in the fields of catalysis, green chemistry, and energy systems. He collaborates with global partners including Petronas, Uppsala University, and Brookhaven National Laboratory, contributing to projects on advanced materials for carbon capture, catalytic conversion pathways, and hydrogen technologies.

Abstract

Achieving Net Zero carbon emissions requires transformative changes in how fuels and chemicals are produced, stored, and utilised. This seminar explores emerging process-intensified technologies that offer viable pathways toward deep decarbonisation, with a particular focus on hydrogen as a flexible energy vector. The talk discusses recent advances in membrane reactor engineering for hydrogen production, highlighting how the integration of reaction and separation in a single intensified unit can overcome thermodynamic limitations, enhance conversion, reduce energy demand, and enable compact, modular systems suitable for distributed hydrogen generation.

Alongside production, hydrogen storage remains a key bottleneck for large-scale deployment. The seminar examines Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs) as a promising solution capable of delivering safe, high-density, and infrastructure-compatible storage. Recent developments in catalytic dehydrogenation/hydrogenation mechanisms, material selection, and reactor design will be presented, with emphasis on techno-economic and lifecycle considerations relevant to Net Zero targets.

Bio-redox based leaching of precious metals from e-wastes

Zahra Ilkhani

Lancaster University, School of Engineering

Abstract

Recycling metals from electronic waste is recognised as a practical approach to addressing the environmental challenges they generate, ensuring human safety and conserving natural resources. Among recycling methods, bioleaching stands out as a sustainable and green technology for metal solubilisation using microorganisms. In this study, pure copper was recovered from waste printed circuit boards using an indirect approach involving sequential bioleaching and electrowinning. The bacterium *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* was cultivated in a stirred tank reactor for the continuous production of ferric iron (Fe^{3+}) as the primary leaching agent and followed by batch leaching at various pulp densities (1%, 2%, 4%, 6% and 8% w/v) at 40 °C for 96 hours, leading to a leaching rate of 50% copper with a pulp density of 6% w/v. The finding was used in a continuous-flow leaching investigation in a stirred-tank reactor, and 100% and 80% of the copper were leached at 40 °C. A hydraulic residence time of 96 hours, with and without pH control, respectively, and later, around 70.85% of pure copper was recovered from the metal-rich solution by electrowinning at a current density of 0.0168 A/cm² over 8 hours. These results provide valuable insights into the continuous recovery of copper from electronic waste, which contributes to the design and optimisation of the process for industrial-scale applications.

Modelling uranium reactive separation from seawater

Steve McGowan

Lancaster University, School of Engineering

Abstract

The potential for extracting uranium from seawater is the subject of ongoing scientific research worldwide, but the classical modelling approach relies on experimental data and empirical models. An analytical expression used to simulate the effects of pH and redox potential (E) on inorganic particles in groundwater conditions provided one path to build this model. Adapting it to the sorption of uranium onto bioorganic model particles in saline environments requires numerous adaptations, including different binding sites and multidentate binding. These novel features will be explained in detail, with a demonstration of how they map to real measurements.

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